

Investigating the Geographic Variation of Hospital Readmission in Italy: What Are the Length-of-Stay and Readmission Cost Trade-Offs?

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ABSTRACT

Background: Since the recent financial crisis, the Italian central government had employed stringent measurements to shorten hospitalization after major surgeries, reduce number of hospital beds, and promote lower but more appropriate hospital admissions. These cost-containment efforts, along with the decentralized healthcare system, may have produced substantial regional variations in early discharges and consequent unplanned readmissions.

Objective: This paper aims to (i) identify the patient and hospital factors that influence the propensity of elderly early readmission, (ii) examine how the risk of readmission varies across regions in Italy, (iii) understand what are the hospital behaviours that potentially drive the quality disparity. We pay special attention to the hospitals' incentive structures and the trade-offs between length-of-stay and readmission cost across regions and hospital ownerships.

Data and Methods: We use the hospital discharge data from 2010 to 2015 for patients above 65 years old admitted with acute myocardial infarction (AMI) (462,044 patients) given the high volume of readmitted patients. We also merge the dataset with hospital-level information that contained bed counts and quality indicators. We first employ a multilevel cox proportional hazard model for time to readmission with patient- and hospital level covariates to identify the degree of variations of readmission risks across hospitals and regions. Given the substantial variation, we base our empirical analysis on a theoretical model where we capture hospitals' discharge incentives in response to payment systems and penalty rules. A two-part model with instrumental variable (for length-of-stay) was used investigate the impact of length-of-stay on probability of readmission and the trade-offs between length-of-stay and readmission cost.

Analysis and Discussion: We find that female, education, and discharged to institution, along with several comorbidities are negative associated with propensity for readmission. Moreover, hospitals with higher AMI patient volume and lower capacities have lower readmission, and public trust, teaching trust as well as private clinics have lower probability of readmission than local health authority directly managed hospitals. After adjusting for patient- and hospital- level indicators, there is substantial geographic variation in elderly readmission and contextual effects on the risk, with intra-class correlations 42.16% at hospital and 25.64% at regional level. The analysis on the trade-off between length-of-stay and readmission cost showed that length-of-stay reduces probability of readmission, and on average, increasing length-of-stay would reduce overall episode cost (index hospitalization and readmission cost). However, the offsetting effects are considerably different across regions and hospital types, reflecting disparate discharge behaviours. The results shed light on the cost-saving incentives of the providers and on the drivers for variation in healthcare quality in Italy and in countries that have decentralized healthcare system.